

THE USE OF TIME-OF-FLIGHT SECONDARY ION MASS SPECTROMETRY
(TOF SIMS) AND EPOXIDE MOLECULAR PROBES TO STUDY
THE INTERFACE IN CARBON FIBRE EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Comparative surface analytical studies of Type A carbon fibres using time-of-flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (TOF SIMS) and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) has demonstrated that the oxygen concentration of the direct surface appears to saturate at a lower degree of fibre treatment (DFT) than previously considered. Attempts to quantify the available functional groups for reaction with epoxy probe molecules has been achieved by TFAA derivatisation. Surface induced polymerisation of epichlorohydrin has also been observed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibres are used extensively in combination with epoxy resins to form composite materials with desirable mechanical properties. To increase the interfacial bond strength it is common practice to anodically oxidise the fibre surface. The effect of the degree of fibre treatment (DFT) on laminate properties is generally monitored using an interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) test. It is known that this reaches a plateau as the interfacial strength approaches the shear strength of the matrix¹. The commercial treatment is chosen to optimise the stress transfer between the fibre and matrix whilst maintaining a satisfactory fracture toughness and impact performance. Full understanding requires correlation of the micromechanical performance with the chemical reactivity of the surface.

XPS has been used to provide chemical analysis of the top 9 nm of the carbon fibre surface², allowing for quantification of the surface atomic species. Attempts to interpret the increase in oxygen concentration as the formation of specific chemical functionalities however, has proved more difficult. Chemical state information can be extracted from the core level envelopes but for industrially treated fibres differentiation between the chemical environments of the oxygen and nitrogen atoms

is beyond the sensitivity of current instruments. As a consequence only highly oxidised fibres can be reliably analysed in this manner. Sherwood³ was able to quantify the oxygen and nitrogen functionalities by applying curve fitting routines to the core level envelopes but interpretation of the industrial treatment levels could only be obtained by extrapolation.

Our approach has involved labelling the functional groups with moieties of high XPS cross-section. To this end we were able to identify the role of acid groups and microporosity using barium and chloroform labelling respectively^{4,5}. More recently we simulated the interaction of a matrix resin with the fibre surface by back titration after treatment with a typical epoxy resin⁶. In this paper, this approach has been extended to other functional groups and epoxy molecular probes.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Instrumentation XPS analysis was carried out on a VG combined lens analyser (CLAM100)-Mg/Al dual anode X-ray source system. Mg radiation was used throughout at a power of 250 W with the fibres oriented parallel to the gun-analyser plane and angled to maximise the Cls signal. TOF SIMS was carried out on a VG IX23LS instrument, equipped with a pulsed 30 keV gallium liquid metal ion gun and Poschenreider analyser. All SIMS spectra discussed were obtained within the static regime i.e. less than 10^{-13} ions cm^{-2} .

2.2 Electrolytic Oxidation of Type AU Fibres Unoxidised Type AU fibres (Hercules Inc) were electrochemically oxidised anodically, using an ammonium bicarbonate electrolyte, up to and beyond the level of commercially treated fibres, as indicated by the analysis of unsized commercially treated AS fibres. The degrees of fibre surface treatment (DFT) were chosen to provide a range of fibre matrix adhesion as determined in an interlaminar shear strength test. The degrees of fibre treatment, DFT, have been quantified by the current density flowing through the cell.

2.3 Trifluoroacetic Anhydride (TFAA) Labelling The samples were subjected to a saturated atmosphere of TFAA (obtained from 2 cm^3 of liquid) contained in a PTFE sealed polycarbonate desiccator (without desiccant) for an allotted exposure time. The excess TFAA was removed by pumping down to a vacuum of approximately 10^{-1} Pa.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Comparison of Surface Information from TOF SIMS and XPS The surface oxygen and nitrogen concentrations in the 9 nm depth sampled by XPS for the range of surface treatment levels are presented in Fig 1. The surface atomic composition of the commercially available unsized AS fibre was found to be 84.9% carbon, 10.8% oxygen, 4.1% nitrogen and 0.2% chlorine. This corresponds to the level of oxidation achieved in our cell at approximately 10 Cm^{-2} . The chlorine signal from the AS fibres, at the limit of detection of our instrument, is a contaminant not found on the surface of the AU fibres, nor AU fibres subsequently oxidised.

The TOF SIMS technique provides higher surface sensitivity at approximately 1 nm whilst giving complementary molecular structural information. However the carbon fibre spectra are dominated by hydrocarbon fragments from the fibre and adsorbed contaminants, remnants of the precursor and subsequent processing. For example remnants of the polyacrylonitrile precursor are present in all fibre spectra as typified by, Na^+ , Cl^- , SO_3 , SO_4^- , HSO_4^- , CN^- , CNO^- and C_2N_3^- in figure 2. The phthalate ion, which is indicative of plasticiser adsorption from the packaging film was also detected. This contamination could also have arisen from the use of PVC tubing to transport washing water. Briggs and Hearne⁷ have discussed in detail the assignments associated with the fibre species detected. Contrary to their findings, we detected no ions indicative of monostearate on untreated fibres. Thus the SIMS spectra from carbon fibres are complex and frequently irreproducible because the peaks arise from contaminants and artifacts of the production process.

Fig.1: Atomic concentration of surface oxygen and nitrogen as determined by XPS versus degree of fibre treatment for Type A carbon fibres.

Whilst no definite pattern could be discovered from the relative intensities of most of the peaks, the O^- and nitrogenated fragments CN^- , CNO^- and C_2N_3^- follow the trend shown in Fig 3. It is seen that oxygen saturation of the surface has occurred between 100 and 250 Cm^{-2} . This represents the top monolayer so that comparison of the increase in atomic concentration of oxygen as determined by XPS, can enhance the understanding of the kinetics of oxidation. Since the analysis depth is greater for

XPS, Fig 1 appears to indicate the formation of subsurface oxygen species continuing beyond the DFT corresponding to surface saturation. This is indicative of the saturation of surface edge sites with oxygen functionalities. It had previously been observed that the surface of Type II fibres was saturated with XPS determinable carboxylic acid groups⁸.

Fig.2: Typical ToF SIMS spectra from Type AU carbon fibres.

Type A fibres have a more disordered structure than those of Type I for which a surface micropore model has been proposed^{4,5}. However a similar structure, although more disordered, must exist with edges of the basal planes providing the active functional sites. The trend for the nitrogen fragments (Fig 3) would suggest that nitrogen-terminated basal planes are being exposed. However at the highest degree of overoxidation the intensity of the CN⁻ declines. This may indicate oxidation or burial of the nitrogen containing sites. Chloroform labelling proved unsuccessful at detecting surface micropores of the dimensions found in Type I

fibres. Therefore as could be expected the surface microporosity is less well developed. In view of the stereochemical aspects of the matrix-fibre interaction⁹, it follows that the top surface functionality may correlate more closely to the micromechanics than that determined by XPS. Unfortunately the SIMS process cannot be effectively quantified so that we have resorted to the use of epoxy probe molecules which can be expected to react with the available surface functionality.

3.2 Estimation of Surface Functionality by Probe Molecules Trifluoroacetic anhydride (TFAA) has been used in the polymer field to quantify surface hydroxyl group concentration by utilizing the reaction shown below. In the vapour phase it has been shown, using model polymers, to react exclusively with hydroxyl groups under ambient conditions. The resulting ester contains three fluorine atoms which have a high cross section for photo-emission, allowing quantification of the functionality by XPS.

When reacted with carbon fibres the surface fluorine concentration did not reach a plateau with exposure time but a maximum. It was also observed that the fluorine concentration, in contrast to model polymers, was not stable in air. The most likely explanation, that the ester groups were being hydrolysed with time, was confirmed by the retention of the fluorine in a moisture free environment (i.e., 10^{-1} Pa). The most plausible explanation for the instability of the surface groups on the carbon fibre, and not the polyvinyl alcohol, must lie with the acidity of the fibre and may well involve catalysis associated with local surface acidity. This could result from TFAA adsorption or the presence of surface carboxylic acid groups. The latter has received intensive consideration elsewhere⁴ and are widely considered to react with the epoxy functionality in the resins. In either case fixation and hydrolysis will be in competition. To minimise hydrolysis, rapid transfer from the evacuated container, used to remove excess TFAA, to the spectrometer was employed.

Using these conditions the fluorine signal for TFAA labelled carbon fibres was used to determine the atomic percentage of hydroxyl groups. These were found to follow a similar trend to that seen in Figure 1. It is concluded therefore that the subsurface hydroxyl groups are accessible to the TFAA molecule (Fig 4).

The concentration of available surface hydroxyl groups as a fraction of the total oxygen can also be determined from the fluorine and oxygen levels. This decreased with DFT and can be correlated with an increase in the proportion of oxygen involved in acid functionalities as determined by barium labelling⁴. This is as expected, i.e., a preference for the formation of acid groups as opposed to hydroxyl functionalities, under more oxidising conditions.

Fig.3: Normalised O⁻ and CN⁻ ion ToF SIMS intensities for Type A carbon fibres of varying degree of surface treatment (DFT).

Fig.4: Surface atomic concentration of hydroxyl groups on Type A carbon fibres of varying degrees of surface treatment (DFT), as estimated by TFAA labelling.

The relatively large fraction of OH groups on the untreated (AU) fibre surface would suggest that hydroxyl group formation is less probable during electrolytic oxidation, than as a result of surface oxidation on removal from the carbonisation furnace. As would be expected these do not account for 100% of the oxygen. The remainder is envisaged to be present as adsorbed water, carbonyl and ester groups.

3.3 Determination of epoxy reactable carboxylic acid groups

3.3.1 Bisphenol 'A' epoxy resin The conventional resin chemistry suggests that the surface carboxylic acid groups should react with the epoxide group in the formation of the interfacial bond. Denison et al⁶ demonstrated the probability of this reaction using back titration of the acid groups with barium labellant showing the remaining acid groups available for reaction to be negligible. For reaction with the epoxide, each acid group should yield one hydroxyl group. Upon treatment of AS fibre with the diglycidylether of bisphenol A (DGEBA), SIMS analysis demonstrated the formation of a continuous film of approximately monolayer thickness. This was deduced from the reduction in the relative CN⁻ intensity and the low attenuation of the surface nitrogen concentration in XPS, from 4.1 to 3.0 atomic %. Using TFAA derivatisation the hydroxyl concentration of the epoxy coated fibre was found to have increased three times. This confirms the reaction of the epoxy functionalities with surface acid groups and the formation of hydroxyl groups as expected. Assuming the reaction had occurred quantitatively it can be determined that this fluorine level is equivalent to a surface acid concentration of approximately 2.6 atomic %. Thus 48% of the XPS detectable surface oxygen atoms are present as acid groups, and 15% as hydroxyl functionality. These results can be compared to barium labelling which indicated that 60% of surface oxygen atoms on industrial Type II fibre was present as acid groups⁴. Barium labelling work is in progress on Type A fibres for direct comparison of the two techniques for quantifying surface acidity.

3.3.2 Surface induced polymerisation For comparative XPS and ToF SIMS studies the epoxide molecule, epichlorohydrin has much potential for modelling the fibre-matrix interface. After adsorption from bulk monomer at 120°C, the hydroxyl group concentration only increased by 30%, as determined by TFAA derivatisation, indicating a different reaction mechanism. The ToF SIMS spectra were characterised by the presence of high molecular weight fragments indicative of surface induced polymerisation, to form a polypropylene oxide structure. XPS also demonstrated the non-stoichiometric retention of chlorine, which inferred that the initial reaction occurred at surface carboxylic acid groups, followed by dehydrochlorination and epoxy ring formation which subsequently polymerised giving a polymeric coating containing both organic and inorganic chlorine residues. The complex nature of this reaction has been reported previously¹⁰. This work which demonstrated high polymer formation and a complex chemistry will be discussed fully elsewhere¹¹.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Comparative ToF SIMS and XPS appears to show that the oxygen concentration saturates at the outermost surface of the carbon fibre while the subsurface appears to continue to oxidise. Furthermore under the chosen experimental conditions, the surface carboxylic acid groups react with epoxy resins to form a monolayer coverage. Derivatisation of hydroxyl groups formed in this reaction has enabled the number of surface acid groups available for reaction with the resin to be quantified.

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